

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

EFFICIENCY OF FERTILIZERS AND BEE-POLLINATION FOR THE ECOLOGICAL FUNCTION OF LEGUMES IN NATURAL ECOSYSTEMS AND AGROCENOSIS OF ARARAT VALLEY IN THE REPUBLIC OF ARMENIA

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ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ УДОБРЕНИЙ НА ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКУЮ ФУНКЦИЮ БОБОВЫХ В ПРИРОДНЫХ ЭКОСИСТЕМАХ И АГРОЦЕНОЗАХ АРАРАТСКОЙ ДОЛИНЫ РЕСПУБЛИКИ АРМЕНИИ

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Abstract

The researches concerning the impact of organic-mineral fertilizers and bee-pollination on the ecological function of legumes in natural phytocenosis and agrocenosis (in ordinary brown soils) of Ararat valley of the Republic of Armenia. It has been found out, that those knobs on legume roots in natural ecosystems and agrocenosis are determined both with legume kind and ecological conditions of its growth. The efficiency of dose usage of organic (organomix and biohumus) and mineral fertilizers, bacterization with rhizopeat, as well as of bee-pollination for increasing the activity of symbiosizing apparatus of legumes has been determined.

Аннотация

В работе изложены исследования влияния органо-минеральных удобрений на экологическую функцию бобовых и естественных фитоценозов и агроценозах (на бурых окультуренных почвах) Араратской долины РА. Выявлено, что формирование клубеньков на корнях бобовых и естественных экосистемах и агроценозах определяется видом бобовых культур и экологическими условиями их произрастания. Установлена эффективность применения доз органических (органомикс, биогумус) и минеральных удобрений, бактериализации ризоторфином, а также пчелоопыления на повышение активности симбиозирующего аппарата у бобовых.

Keywords: ecosystem, biohumus, organomix, organic-mineral fertilizers, legumes.

Ключевые слова. Экосистем, биогумус, органомикс, органо-минеральных удобрений, бобовые.

The extreme scarce application of mineral nitrogenous fertilizers in agrocenosis, as well as in natural ecosystems has led to the situation, when the unique way of maintaining the equilibrium is biological fixation of atmospheric nitrogen.

A great and still growing interest to the problem of biological fixation of nitrogen with symbiotic and free living microorganisms is based on the paradox, that in spite of the enormous reserves of nitrogen in the atmosphere, nitrogen is a limiting factor of the productivity of the ecosystems. Therefore, the comparison of the ecological function of legumes in natural ecosystems and agrocenosis is highly important in determining real

possibilities of penetration of pure biologically bound nitrogen into the soil.

Microorganisms, which possess the capacity of entering symbiotic interrelation with higher plants when forming root knobs, are of the greatest interest to agriculture. It is considered, that depending on whether the plants are annual or perennial symbiotic systems of legumes fix from 100 kg up to 300 kg/ha of nitrogen annually. However, nowadays it is impossible to judge of the role of legumes in replenishing nitrogen fund in natural ecosystems and agrocenosis. The investigation of this issue has become one of the main tasks of the researches carried out by us.

We have studied knob formation on the roots of legumes, e.g. clover, alfalfa, and vetch, in natural phytocenosis, i.e. on the ordinary black earth soil of the short-footed meadow with different grass of Martunie Region in the Republic of Armenia. The formation of knobs on the roots of holy clover, clover and bean in agroecosystem has been studied on the leached black earth soil in the same region.

The tests were carried out in three reiterations. Field tests on alfalfa were carried while applying mineral fertilizers $N_{60}P_{60}K_{60}$, $N_{90}P_{90}K_{90}$ and organic fertilizers, i.e. organomix 4,0 and 60t/ha dose and biohumus in 2 and 3 t/ha one. Bacterization of alfalfa seeds was carried out with fresh made rhizopeat having the titre of 21 milliard cells in 1g of peat, local active strain of knob bacteria got from alfalfa knobs. One kilogram of rhizopeat was spent on a kilogram of seeds.

While carrying out the tests knob formed on a plant were counted, and their shape, size, colour and allocation on the roots as well as fixation of atmospheric nitrogen were estimated.

The results received have shown that the accumulation of nitrogen by nodule bacteria of legumes in the soil is connected with the amount of knobs on the roots, their size and physiological activity. There is a considerable amount of knobs in natural phytocenosis of clover, alfalfa, and vetch in the phase of flowering. They make up 185, 115 and 31 correspondingly, and sometimes even exceed the amount on legumes of agroecosystem. The amount of knobs on a plant in the examples

with holy clover is equal to 92 ± 12 and it is 168 ± 15 in the one with clover.

Tiny (less than 1 mm) and low-active in fixing molecular nitrogen knobs of green and white colour are found on the roots of legumes under natural conditions. On the contrary all the knobs on the roots holy clover, alfalfa, clover, and legumes were pink, i.e. possessed high physiological activity in fixing nitrogen of atmosphere.

According to our data, bacteria excreted from the knobs of legumes in leached black earth soil are characterized by their high physiological activity, the size of colonies and their growth rate, comparing to the ones from natural phytocenosis. It means that ecological condition have their influence on the knob formation considerably and hence on the process of biological nitrogen fixation. Most likely it is connected with the impact of moisture and temperature restricting the assimilation of nutrients, when their combination is unfavorable.

The results of the tests while using mineral and organic fertilizers for alfalfa grown in brown earth soils have shown that the application of a whole mineral fertilizer having $N_{60}P_{60}K_{60}$ dose and 10t/ha of organic one dose not supply humus and nutrients and dose not lead to the increase of the amount of knobs. The increase of biological nitrogen fixation is twice as much while applying mineral fertilizers having (NPK)90 dose, 60 t/ha of organomix and 2 or 3 t/ha of biohumus (Table 1).

Table 1

Impact of mineral and organic fertilizers on knob formation of alfalfa roots

№	Versions	Amount of knobs on plant, mg	Weight of raw knobs on a plant, mg	Knob size, mm			
				<1	<2	<3	<4
1	$N_{60}P_{60}K_{60}$	7	4,3	2	4	1	-
2	$N_{90}P_{90}K_{90}$	13	6,6	4	6	2	1
3	Organomix 4t/ha	6	3,0	2	2	2	-
4	Organomix 6 t/ha	14	6,8	4	7	2	1
5	Biohumus 2 t/ha	13	6,4	4	6	2	1
6	Biohumus 3 t/ha	15	7,5	5	7	2	1

As to bacterization of alfalfa with rhizopeat, the efficiency of bacterization differed depending on plant density and spacing. Alfalfa has formed the greatest amount of knobs in 15 sm spacing with plant density equal to 9 and 13 million items per a hectare. Sowing

at 5 kg dose per 1 hectare with plant spacing equal to 15 sm has also increased the amount of knobs, but has not promoted their weight increase, that's why it cannot be considered effective (Table 2).

Table 2

Impact of mineral and organic fertilizers on knob formation of alfalfa roots

Spacing, sm	Sowing norm, million items per ha	Amount of knobs on plant roots	Weight of raw knobs on a plant, mg	Knob size, mm			
				<1	<2	<3	<4
15	13	11	2,60	8	2	1	-
15	9	12	2,20	7	2	3	-
15	5	14	1,70	8	2	3	1
60	5	9	1,40	3	3	3	-

One of the ways of improving the growth of knobs on legume roots is considered to be bee-pollination. (Table 3) Comparing to the control version (without bee-pollination) 2,5-3 times more knobs has formed on the roots of holy clover grown at a short distance from

an apiary. Nevertheless, nitrogen accumulation in the soil by biological fixation depends not only on the amount of knobs on the roots, but also on their size and physiological activity, which depend on bee-pollination in their turn.

Table 3

Impact of bee-pollination on the amount and composition of knobs on the roots of plants
(average of three reiterations)

Plants	Distance from an apiary, m	Amount of knobs on a plant root	Knob weight on a plant	Knobs size		
Holy clover	at an apiary	53 ± 5	0,40	85%	15%	-
	700	125 ± 10	0,48	60%	30%	10%
	2400	24 ± 5	0,28	85%	15%	-
Clover	at an apiary	265 ± 23	0,46	60%	30%	10%
	700	295 ± 40	0,60	45%	28%	27%
	2400	140 ± 24	0,30	80%	29%	-

In the versions with bee-pollination bigger equilibrium in biosphere legumes must occupy not pink knobs which are characterized by their high activity of symbiosizing systems were forming.

Thus, not only an additional application of energetic resources in the agrocenosis, but also an active bee-pollination leads to the intensification of the process of symbiotic nitrogen fixation of legumes.

Legumes in a grass covering of natural cenosis in different regions of Sevan Lake basin occupy unequal areas. It means that the ecological function of legume in highland regions will be more noticeable while providing optimal conditions for the formation of knob bacteria. On the whole the biological fixation of nitrogen in natural phytocenosis takes place on an area not exceeding 12-14% of a grass covering. As to agrocenosis, the areas can be regulated. In order not to break the equilibrium in biosphere must occupy not less than 10-15% of farm lands.

Thus, summarizing the above-stated we can conclude, that:

1. Knob formation on legume roots in natural ecosystems and agrocenosis is determined by the type of legumes and ecological conditions of their growing.

2. Doses of organic (biohumus 2-3 t/ha, organomix 6,0) and mineral fertilizers (N₉₀P₉₀K₉₀), bacterization with rhizopeat, as well as bee-pollination are to be effective means of increasing the activity of symbiosizing apparatus of legumes.

3. Applying biohumus at rates equal to 2 t/ha and 3 t/ha have a more effective impact on a symbiosizing apparatus of legumes, than applying organomix at a rate of 2 t/ha and whole mineral fertilizer in a dose of N₉₀P₉₀K₉₀.

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